

Mixed ligand complexes of manganese, cobalt and zinc with 2-pyridinealdoxime and some neutral ligands

S. C. Nayak^{a*}, P. K. Das^b and K. K. Sahoo^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, B. N. M. A. College, Paliabindha, Bhadrak-756 167, India

E-mail : saratnayak1@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, F. M. College, Balasore-756 001, India

^cP. G. Department of Chemistry, Bhadrak College, Bhadrak-756 100, India

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Complexes of the type [ML₂B₂], where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, L = 2-pyridinealdoxime, B = neutral ligands (benzimidazole, benzotriazole, triazole, carbazole) and [MLB₂]Cl, where M = Zn^{II}, have been synthesized. The zinc complexes dissociate in solution. The Co^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes are paramagnetic but the Zn^{II} complexes are diamagnetic in nature. The results reveal octahedral geometry for the Mn^{II} and Co^{II} complexes and tetrahedral geometry for the Zn^{II} complexes.

There is growing interest in the studies on the metal complexes with various biologically important ligands¹. 2-Pyridinealdoxime, benzimidazole, benzotriazole, triazole and carbazole are biologically active compounds. Here we report the synthesis and characterization of Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with the above mentioned ligands.

Results and discussion

The coloured microcrystalline complexes (Table 1) have m.ps. >240°. All the Zn complexes are white, stable at room temperature and highly soluble in dioxane and dimethylformamide. The analytical data indicate 1 : 2 : 2 metal : 2-pyridinealdoxime : neutral ligand stoichiometry for all the Co^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes but 1 : 1 : 2 stoichiometry for the Zn^{II} complexes. The conductance values (in DMF) of the Mn^{II} and Co^{II} complexes (10–19 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) indicate their non-electrolytic nature, however, higher values (40–60 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) of the Zn^{II} complexes indicate their 1 : 1 electrolytic nature.

IR spectra of 2-pyridinealdoxime (PA) show a broad and medium band around 3100–3000 cm⁻¹ assigned to CH stretch of aromatic ring. The ligand band at 2900 cm⁻¹ (OH) disappears in the complexes, indicating the replacement of phenolic hydrogen by metal ion. The band² at 1570 cm⁻¹ (C=N of pyridyl-N) of the ligand is shifted to lower energy by 10–15 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, indicating the involvement of pyridyl-N on coordination. The band³ at 1610 cm⁻¹ (C=N) in the metal complexes is similar to that of 2-pyridinealdoxime. This indicates that nitrogen of oxime group is not bonded to the metal ion. The band^{4,5} at 425

cm⁻¹ is due to the coordination of nitrogen (N-1) atom in the neutral ligands (bmz, btz, tria, car) to the metal ion in the complexes.

Table 1. Analytical data of the complexes*

Compd.**	Colour	Analysis % :	
		Found/(calcd.)	
		Metal	Cl
[Co pa ₂ bmz ₂]	Orange	10.99 (10.96)	–
[Co pa ₂ btz ₂]	Yellow	10.96 (10.94)	–
[Co pa ₂ tria ₂]	Green	13.42 (13.43)	–
[Co pa ₂ car ₂]	Brown	9.25 (9.29)	–
[Mn pa ₂ bmz ₂]	Pink	10.28 (10.31)	–
[Mn pa ₂ btz ₂]	Yellow	10.27 (10.28)	–
[Mn pa ₂ tria ₂]	Orange	12.61 (12.64)	–
[Mn pa ₂ car ₂]	Pink	8.76 (8.71)	–
[Zn pa bmz ₂]Cl	White	14.21 (14.2)	7.72 (7.75)
[Zn pa btz ₂]Cl	White	14.15 (14.14)	7.65 (7.61)
[Zn pa tria ₂]Cl	White	18.09 (18.08)	9.85 (9.87)
[Zn pa car ₂]Cl	White	11.73 (11.7)	6.35 (6.39)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analyses. **pa = 2-pyridinealdoxime, bmz = benzimidazole, btz = benzotriazole, tria = triazole, car = carbazole

The electronic spectra (in DMSO) of the Co^{II} complexes show bands at 9500 and 18000 cm⁻¹, assigned to transitions ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F), respectively. It suggests an octahedral geometry around the metal ion⁶. The magnetic moment values⁷ (4.5–4.9 B.M.) also support the structure [Co pa₂ L₂]. The Mn^{II} complexes show bands at 14000, 16500 and 19500 cm⁻¹, assigned to transitions ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(⁴G), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(⁴G) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴E_g, ⁴A_{1g}

(4G), respectively, suggesting octahedral geometry around the metal ion⁸. The magnetic moment value (5.9–6.1 B.M.) also supports the structure $[Mn pa_2 L_2]$. All the Zn complexes $[Zn pa L_2]$ are diamagnetic. On the basis of spectral data, tetrahedral geometry is suggested for the zinc complexes.

The evidence for the bonding mode of the ligand is provided by the 1H NMR spectra of the metal complexes. The ligand 2-pyridinealdoxime shows signal at δ 9.82 ($-CH=N-$), which shifted to δ 9.92 in the complexes. The signal at δ 11.4 (OH) in the free ligand is absent in the complexes, thus confirming the deprotonation of OH group on complex formation. The positions of the ligand signals due to H-3 and H-4 proton in the pyridine moiety at δ 7.45 and 7.54 shift towards lower field in the complex at δ 7.4 and 7.51, respectively. The signals for hydrogen in the neutral heterocyclic ligand generally appears at δ 6.51–8.53, which are shifted slightly upfield on coordination.

In the ^{13}C NMR spectra, the carbon atom (C=N) signal in the 2-pyridinealdoxime appears at 162.7 ppm, which is not shifted in the complex. The signals due to carbon atoms C-2, C-3, C-4 of 2-pyridinealdoxime appear at 149.4, 123.5, 135.7 ppm, respectively. These signals are shifted downfield at around 152.3, 124, 136.9 ppm, respectively, in the complexes.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The metal complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of an aqueous ethanolic solution of the metal chloride (0.05 mol in 40 ml), 2-pyridinealdoxime (0.1 mol) and neutral ligands (benzimidazole, benzotriazole, triazole, carbazole; 0.1 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) on a steam-bath for 30 min. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo* over anhyd. $CaCl_2$.

The metals were analyzed by standard procedures⁹. C,

H and N were estimated using a Carlo-Erba-1108 analyzer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-15 spectrophotometer and 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Broker-DRX-300 (300 MHz) FTNMR spectrometer. Conductance was measured in 10^{-3} M DMF solution with a Systronic-303 conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by a Gouy balance using diamagnetic correction by Pascal's constant.

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